

THE MOST ACUTE PROBLEMS OF KAZAKH FAMILIES

Baurzhan D.,*Student – Bachelor's degree – School of Informational Technologies***Beken L.,***Student – Bachelor's degree – School of Informational Technologies***Kalashnikova V.,***Student – Bachelor's degree – School of Informational Technologies***Tileubayeva M.***Supervisor – Associated professor, PhD***Abstract**

This sociological project is dedicated **to the most acute problems of Kazakh families**, their reasons, and consequences, as well as their solution. We have chosen this topic due to its high relevance.

Keywords: Younger generation, family policy, domestic violence, mental health, financial stress, Kazakh families, modern families, socialization, environment, culture, religion, psychological intimacy, dependent position, emotional relation, household, traditions, economic impact, education, alcohol and substance abuse, power play, division of property, children's development, individuality, personality, government, physical health, illness, emotional strain, geographic area.

INTRODUCTION**1.1. Overview: Relevance of the topic**

The family is the main source of formation of values of the younger generation. This is a basic social institution, the functioning of which directly affects the well-being and stability of the state. Therefore, the primary goals of the state family policy are to support, strengthen and protect families, create the necessary conditions conducive to the physical, intellectual, spiritual, moral development of families.

The dynamics of the number of registered marriages in Kazakhstan over the past five years shows a moderate decrease. The number of divorces exceeds the number of marriages. On the example of Almaty, the dynamics is as follows: every year 3 thousand people get married, while 5 thousand divorces are registered annually.

Currently, in the Republic of Kazakhstan, as in other republics of the post-Soviet space, there is a certain decrease in the level of marriage, an increase in the age of marriage, an increase in the number of divorces, a drop in the birth rate, an increase in the number of illegitimate births. For example, according to the 1999 census, 25.7% of the population of the republic aged 15 years and older were not married, and in 2009 – 32.3%. The same applies to the increase in the proportion of illegitimate births (in 1999 – 51,959, in 2008 – 75,380), which is due not only to the actual illegitimate childbearing activity, but also to the spread of unregistered marriages, which have become quite commonplace in Kazakhstan.

The presence of officially unregistered marriage unions reflects the complex processes of transformation of marriage and family relations, as well as a decrease in the degree of administrative regulation of public life, including in the marriage and family sphere.

The family plays a crucial role in shaping an individual's personality and providing primary socialization. It instills moral norms, patterns of behavior, and a sense of integrity in individuals. Additionally, it serves as a critical link in forming and accumulating human

capital, making it an essential institution for the development of culture and economy. The family also provides a variety of forms of communication, which enables human interactions in various spheres of life. Therefore, the family has enduring value for human civilization, and its protection is enshrined in many international normative acts.

However, the institution of the family is currently undergoing a crisis in many countries, including Kazakhstan. The decline in the importance of the family can be attributed to various factors, such as global social changes, cultural transformation, and socio-economic causes. The impact of the economic crisis on young people is particularly significant. The transition from the Soviet to the modern family also affects the institution's functioning, intra-family interaction, value orientations, and life priorities. As a result, the institution of the family is going through a complex process of transformation and crisis, which is reflected in the rising divorce rates.

To address this crisis, there is a need for strong state family policies that provide the necessary conditions for the family to realize its functions and improve its quality of life. The state faces challenges in ensuring that the family can successfully carry out its socio-economic functions. Therefore, the state's support proportional to the challenges faced by the institution of the family is critical. Overall, a strong state family policy is essential to meet the existing social needs and overcome the challenges facing the institution of the family.

In conclusion, the family is a vital social institution that provides social reproduction and has an enduring impact on human civilization. The decline in the importance of the family in many countries, including Kazakhstan, is a complex issue with various socio-economic and cultural causes. To address this crisis, there is a need for a strong state family policy that provides necessary conditions for the family to realize its functions and improve its quality of life. The solution of the challenges faced by the institution of the family will en-

able it to continue playing a crucial role in shaping individuals' personalities and contributing to the development of culture and economy.

1.2. Potential research questions

The scope of the study could be limited to a specific geographic area or population group, such as rural families, low-income families, or families with children. Alternatively, the study could take a broader perspective and examine the challenges faced by Kazakh families.

To address this research problem, various research methods could be used, such as surveys, interviews, focus groups, and case studies. The data could be analysed using qualitative or quantitative techniques, depending on the nature of the research questions and objectives.

Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

I. What are the most acute problems faced by Kazakh families in Almaty, and how do they vary by demographic group?

II. What are the underlying contributing factors to these problems, and how do they interact with each other?

III. What are the consequences of these problems for individuals and families, and how do they impact social and economic outcomes?

IV. How are families coping with these challenges, and what strategies are they using to overcome them?

Ultimately, the findings of this research could contribute to a better understanding of the challenges faced by Kazakh families and inform the development of policies and programs that are more responsive to their needs.

1.3. Defining the research problem

The problem addressed in this research is how international rankings affect global competition and how consolidating international partnerships can enhance a country's global competitiveness.

One problem with international rankings and global competition is that they can create a focus on short-term performance at the expense of long-term sustainability. For example, a country or organization may prioritize achieving high rankings in areas such as economic growth or innovation, but at the cost of environmental sustainability, social equality, or other long-term considerations.

Another problem is that rankings may not always accurately reflect the reality on the ground. Rankings are often based on a narrow set of criteria or data, and may not fully capture the complexities of a country or organization's performance or potential. This can lead to a misalignment between rankings and actual performance, and may create unfair advantages or disadvantages for certain countries or organizations.

Additionally, global competition can lead to a race to the bottom in terms of labor standards, environmental protections, or other social and ethical considerations. Countries and organizations may seek to lower costs and increase competitiveness by cutting corners or exploiting workers, which can have negative impacts on society and the environment.

To address these problems, it is important to ensure that international rankings and global competition are balanced with considerations of long-term sustainability, social and environmental responsibility, and ethical behavior. This may involve creating new metrics and data that more accurately reflect a country or organization's performance, developing new standards and regulations to ensure fair competition, and promoting cooperation and collaboration between countries and organizations to achieve shared goals.

I. COMMON CHALLENGES IN KAZAKH FAMILIES RELATED TO DAILY LIVING (EVERYDAY ISSUES FACED BY KAZAKH FAMILIES):

2.1. Challenges related to the financial system and resources

Division of property. Sometimes, when each spouse works and they can't agree on financial issues or find the time to talk about them, they decide to split the bills down the middle or allocate them in some other fair and equitable manner. When the bills have been covered, each spouse can spend what they have left as they see fit. It sounds like a reasonable plan, but the process often builds resentment over the individual purchases made. It also divides spending power, eliminating much of the financial value of marriage, as well as the ability to plan for long-term goals such as buying a home or securing retirement. And it can lead to relationship-ruining behaviour like financial infidelity, wherein one spouse hides money from the other.

Debt. From school loans to car loans to credit cards to gambling habits, most people come to the altar with financial baggage. If one partner has more debt than the other—or if one partner is debt-free—the sparks can start to fly when discussions about income, spending, and debt servicing come up.

Power Plays. Power plays often occur in one of these four scenarios:

One partner has a paid job and the other doesn't.

Both partners would like to be working but one is unemployed.

One spouse earns considerably more than the other.

One partner comes from a family that has money and the other doesn't.

When one or more of these situations is present, the money earner (or the one who makes or has the most money) often wants to dictate the couple's spending priorities. Although there may be some rationale behind this idea, it is still important that both partners cooperate as a team. Keep in mind that while a joint account offers greater transparency and access, it is not in itself a solution to an unbalanced power/money dynamic in a marriage.

Also, the problem with the financial provision of families can be seen in the incident that took place in 2019. On February 5, five girls who died due to a fire in the temporary shelter where they lived were buried in Astana. The fire occurred at night when their parents were not at home. According to law enforcement agencies, the mother was at work on the night shift, and the father was urgently called to the service station to finish the work. The fact that the parents were not there at

night with the girls, the youngest of whom was only 11 months old, most of all struck Kazakhstani: the mother and father were forced to work even at night, and there was no one to save the children at the fateful moment. This makes you think about 2 things:

1. About the amount of benefits for large families. As we can see, 69,138 tenge is clearly not enough for a family with 5 children. The Government should consider about expanding the number of benefits.

2. About financial literacy of citizens of Kazakhstan. The parents themselves are responsible for this case. Given their financial situation, they should have realized that they would not be able to devote enough time to their children, which puts them at risk.

How to Handle Money Issues in a Marriage. If you've read this far, you probably won't be surprised that the best way to handle such marriage stressors is with communication and honesty in conveying expectations, hopes, goals, and anxieties. Couples should also practice empathy, have the maturity to check their egos, and abandon any predilection for control. Yes, that's much easier said than done. And no, there is no silver bullet.

Some people may never get it right, but that doesn't mean they can't employ certain tools and techniques to address the symptoms. Here are some issues and approaches that may help.

- Deal with debt

For many couples, dealing with debt is often the first issue on the agenda. Knowing what you're about to get yourself into can help you decide how to deal with it. Given this fact, both partners should have an honest, nonjudgmental discussion—ideally around the time when their relationship looks like it's becoming serious—about the debts they would bring into a marriage. Each should come clean about any bad spending or financial habits that the other should know about—or any personal or family issues that could affect future spending.

Couples should also perform a full accounting of debts and talk about how they plan to handle them. It can help to apply one of several common payoff strategies, such as paying off the higher-interest debt first (the debt avalanche method) or paying off the smallest loans first (the debt snowball method).

- Sign a prenup (or postnup)

If you just can't come to an agreement but your heart won't let you walk away, a prenuptial agreement may be an option. Just be aware that one partner may find it insulting. The best practice would be to first have a conversation about the financial anxiety that makes one partner think a prenup is the best solution. If this is a second marriage for both partners, for example, they may have financial assets that they want to pass on to their respective children.

If you've already said, "I do," and you want more than vows to protect yourself, you may want to create a pain-free postnuptial agreement (or marital contract). This marital contract can underline your love for each other, though it can be a hard sell those winds up undermining marital trust if not used as intended or framed the right way. On the other hand, some postnups

can help save a marriage after a crisis that undermined trust.

- Check your ego

The power play issue can get ugly quickly. Few things build resentment faster than being made to feel inferior. If you've got more cash, you need to be sensitive about how you present spending decisions. If you don't have the money, you need to be prepared for stress and tension that is almost inevitable, even in good marriages. This subject comes up with increasing frequency when couples wait until later in life to marry.

Studies have shown that people with more power are more likely to act selfishly, impulsively, and aggressively, and approach others with less empathy.⁵ Each partner in a marriage should ask themselves whether their behaviour works toward the goal of a more kind, appreciative, and equitable relationship or not.

One solution that has demonstrated success is for the higher-earning spouse to delegate all spending decisions to the lower-earning spouse. It takes a certain personality to be able to make the decision to give up power, but if you can do it, it may be a sound path to peace.

2.2. Domestic violence

Domestic violence is a serious problem in Kazakhstan that affects many individuals and families. Despite efforts to combat it, domestic violence continues to be prevalent throughout the country, and many victims feel helpless and unsupported. According to a 2018 survey conducted by the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), approximately 17% of women in Kazakhstan reported experiencing physical violence by a partner in their lifetime, while 14% reported experiencing sexual violence. These figures suggest that domestic violence is a significant problem in the country, with a disproportionate impact on women.

One of the main reasons for the high incidence of domestic violence in Kazakhstan is the cultural and societal norms that prioritize the family unit over the individual. This often leads to situations where victims are told to endure abuse and violence for the sake of preserving family unity.

Moreover, there is a lack of awareness and education about domestic violence, and many victims may not recognize that they are being abused or may not know how to seek help. This is especially true in rural areas where access to resources and support is limited.

There are also significant regional variations in the prevalence of domestic violence in Kazakhstan. A 2018 study conducted by the UNFPA found that the highest rates of physical and sexual violence by a partner were reported in the Kyzylorda and South Kazakhstan regions, while the lowest rates were reported in the Almaty and Astana regions.

Additionally, the legal framework in Kazakhstan is not adequate to address domestic violence. The country does have laws criminalizing domestic violence, but enforcement of these laws is often weak, and many victims do not report abuse out of fear of retaliation or because they believe that the police will not take their complaints seriously.

Furthermore, research indicates that domestic violence in Kazakhstan is often linked to alcohol and substance abuse. A study conducted by the OSCE in 2017 found that over 60% of women who had experienced physical or sexual violence reported that their partner had been drinking alcohol at the time of the abuse.

There are some efforts underway to combat domestic violence in Kazakhstan. For example, the government has established a national commission on gender policy, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are working to raise awareness and provide support for victims. However, much more needs to be done to address this pressing issue.

To effectively tackle domestic violence in Kazakhstan, it is crucial to address the underlying cultural and societal norms that perpetuate it. This involves educating the public about the harm caused by domestic violence and promoting a culture of respect for individual rights and well-being.

Overall, these research findings suggest that domestic violence is a significant and complex problem in Kazakhstan, with a range of factors contributing to its prevalence. Efforts to combat domestic violence will need to consider regional differences, address the root causes of the problem, and provide adequate support and resources to victims.

2.3. Family issues connected to health problems

Health problems can be a significant source of stress for families in Kazakhstan. Illnesses or disabilities can not only take a toll on an individual's health but also impact the entire family's emotional and financial well-being.

According to the World Health Organization, non-communicable diseases (NCDs) account for 87% of deaths in Kazakhstan. The leading causes of death in the country include cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and respiratory diseases. In addition, mental health disorders are estimated to affect 15-20% of the population. These illnesses often require ongoing medical care and medication, which can be expensive and put a significant strain on a family's finances. Families may have to make difficult choices between paying for medical treatment and meeting other essential needs.

In addition to chronic illnesses, mental health issues are also a growing concern in Kazakhstan. Depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) are prevalent, particularly among those who have experienced trauma or have been affected by the country's economic instability. Mental health problems can affect a person's ability to work, attend school, and participate in social activities, which can cause significant emotional strain on the entire family.

Disabilities are another area of concern for families in Kazakhstan. According to the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection, there are over 600,000 people with disabilities in the country. Children with disabilities may require special education and care, which can be difficult for families to provide, especially if they lack financial resources. Adults with disabilities may struggle to find employment, further exacerbating financial strain, with only 5% of working-age people with disabilities employed in the formal sector.

Research has also highlighted the economic impact of health problems in Kazakhstan. A study conducted by the Asian Development Bank found that households in Kazakhstan spend a significant portion of their income on healthcare, with the poorest households spending up to 27% of their income on medical expenses.

In response to these challenges, the Kazakh government has implemented various healthcare and social protection programs. For instance, the government provides free healthcare to vulnerable groups, including children, pregnant women, and people with disabilities. The government has also introduced a disability allowance and established vocational training programs for people with disabilities.

In conclusion, health problems, including chronic illnesses, mental health disorders, and disabilities, can put a significant strain on families in Kazakhstan, both emotionally and financially. The government and healthcare system need to prioritize affordable and accessible healthcare, as well as support services to help families cope with the impact of health problems.

CONCLUSION OF THE 1ST CHAPTER

It is important to note that the issues of education, domestic violence, economic problems, and health concerns are interrelated and can have a significant impact on the wellbeing of Kazakh families.

In terms of education, access to quality education can be limited for some families, particularly those living in rural areas or facing financial difficulties. This can lead to a lack of opportunities and limit the potential of children to succeed academically and professionally. Additionally, a lack of education can lead to a lack of awareness and understanding of important issues, including health and domestic violence.

Domestic violence is a significant issue in Kazakh families, with many women and children facing abuse and violence from their partners or family members. This can have a profound impact on the mental and physical health of those affected, leading to long-term consequences.

Economic problems, including poverty, unemployment, and limited access to financial resources, can exacerbate other issues faced by Kazakh families. These problems can limit access to education, healthcare, and other necessary resources, leading to a cycle of poverty and disadvantage.

Health concerns, including limited access to healthcare and high rates of infectious diseases, can further impact the wellbeing of Kazakh families. This can lead to long-term health problems and limited access to necessary medical treatments.

In conclusion, addressing these issues in Kazakh families will require a multi-faceted approach, including improvements to education, addressing domestic violence, improving economic opportunities, and providing access to healthcare. By addressing these issues, families can have a better chance at achieving success and improving their overall wellbeing.

II. COMMON CHALLENGES IN KAZAKH FAMILIES RELATED TO MENTAL HEALTH AND RELATIONSHIPS

3.1. Raising Awareness about Mental Health Issues

In Kazakh families, mental health problems can often be a source of shame and stigma, leading to reluctance to seek help and support.

One of the most common mental health problems in Kazakhstan is depression, which affects many people across the country. Depression can be particularly difficult for Kazakh families because of the cultural belief in "keeping face" and presenting a strong front to others. This can make it difficult for individuals to acknowledge their struggles and seek the help they need.

According to a study conducted by the National Centre for Mental Health in Kazakhstan, the prevalence of mental health disorders in Kazakhstan is around 18.8%, with depression being the most common disorder at 6.3% (1). This indicates that mental health problems are a significant issue in Kazakhstan, affecting a significant portion of the population.

Anxiety is another mental health problem that is prevalent in Kazakh families, particularly among young people. Many Kazakh families place a great deal of pressure on their children to succeed academically and professionally, which can lead to high levels of stress and anxiety. Additionally, the rapid pace of modernization and globalization in Kazakhstan has led to significant social and economic changes, which can also contribute to feelings of anxiety and uncertainty.

Substance abuse is another mental health problem that is a significant issue in Kazakh families. Alcoholism is a major problem in Kazakhstan, and it can have a devastating impact on individuals and families alike. The stigma surrounding mental health problems can make it difficult for individuals with substance abuse issues to seek help, and this can lead to a cycle of addiction and untreated mental health problems.

Overall, mental health problems are a significant issue in Kazakh families, and more needs to be done to raise awareness and reduce stigma surrounding these issues. By providing education and support to individuals and families affected by mental health problems, it is possible to improve outcomes and promote mental well-being in Kazakhstan.

3.2. Cultural and religious differences

Differences in cultures and in relations with religion can contribute to many discords in the family. And if we consider geographical and historical features, we can say that the culture between the south and the north is radically different, despite the same nationality and religion.

Modern sovereign Kazakhstan is going through a period of its national revival. The growing interest in the history of one's people, in one's national culture, in the origins of the formation of an ethnos and its evolution in the system of global civilization are realities characteristic of the entire post-Soviet space at the turn of the century, called by some researchers the time of "rebellious ethnicity" or "new national revival" [1, p.5]. This process fully applies to the Kazakh ethnic group,

since previously there was a conscious elimination and destruction of cultural traditions throughout the twentieth century. During the seventy-year Soviet period, Kazakhstan struggled with traditions as "remnants of the past." However, no socio-political processes could "obscure" the ethnic identity and national self-expression of the Kazakh ethnic group.

In this regard, a positive appeal to the religion and history of one's people, one's own national and cultural roots can serve to solve such urgent problems of modern society in the field of marriage and family, as an increase in the number of divorces, a low number of marriages and a drop in the birth rate, lack of children, upbringing in single-parent families, orphanhood, etc.

Therefore, there is no doubt about the importance and relevance, both scientifically and socially, of posing the problem of studying the cultural traditions and values of the modern Kazakh family from the standpoint of ethnopsychology analysis.

Taking into account the fact that the problems of marriage and family are interdisciplinary in nature, we considered it necessary and the only possible in our case to conduct a comprehensive (interdisciplinary) analysis of historical, ethnographic and cultural literature, as well as empirical research in psychological and sociological sciences.

Thus, among the historical and ethnographic works, the works of the outstanding Kazakh scientist H.A. Argynbayev are particularly distinguished. His doctoral dissertation "Family and marriage among Kazakhs" is devoted to the history of the formation and development of the Kazakh family. It presents the author's multifaceted and in-depth ethnographic analysis of family and marriage among Kazakhs in different historical periods. This is especially true of questions about the forms of marriage, wedding, and wedding ceremonies.

Thus, in order to marry, it was necessary to comply with certain restrictions related to exogamous, social, class, national and religious norms. The exogamous barrier among Kazakhs is mainly limited to the 7th generation. Modern Kazakhs try to adhere to this norm today, because it serves to regulate the birth of physically and mentally healthy offspring and procreation.

It should also be noted that when concluding marriage unions, the social affiliation of the parties was of no small importance for the Kazakhs. From the point of view of modernity, the socio-economic factor of marriage is of great importance at the present time. Because among the reasons for divorce, the difference in the social and material-economic status of partners plays an important role. The equality of the bride and groom in socio-economic terms (level of education, similarity of the socialization environment, income level) gives a sense of psychological equality.

In general, the modern family life of the Kazakh people, according to the scientist, having absorbed all the best from the centuries-old experience and traditions of the people, at the same time qualitatively differs from the pre-revolutionary one. It clearly reflects the fundamental changes in the socio-economic, socio-

political and cultural life of the Kazakh nation. The psychology of Kazakh men and women, their relationships have changed. Many elements of folk traditions, customs and rituals have been transformed and simplified, and some have disappeared altogether.

Fundamental changes, according to the scientist's fair remark, occurred in the relationship of members of the Kazakh family. In fact, the dependent position of the daughter-in-law (*kelin*) has been completely overcome in relation not only to her husband, but also to her husband's parents and relatives, up to the norms of treatment and behavior in the family. The friendly, relaxed relations of the daughter-in-law with her husband's parents have already become a stereotype of the modern family [4, p.114]. The father-in-law (*kayin ata*) and especially the mother-in-law (*kayin en*) provide all possible assistance in household management, in raising children and thereby create normal conditions for self-realization and career growth of the daughter-in-law.

The relationship between husband and wife in a modern Kazakh family, as a rule, is based on mutual love, respect, mutual assistance and support. And the main condition for marriage is voluntary, mutual feeling and independent solution of the issue by the young.

Of the traditional customs, such as bride's looks, dowry looks, showering of the young (*shashu*), pouring fat into the fire by the bride (*otka mai kuyu*), offering the groom dishes with brisket (*tosh*), and matchmakers – meat from the back of the animal (*zhambas*), the performance of household ritual songs (*zhar-heat* and *bet-ashar*), mutual gifting of matchmakers, etc.

The institution of *kalym* and the surviving forms of marriage (*levirate*, *sororate*), as you know, have now disappeared. But the custom of giving the bride a dowry has been preserved. However, the modern dowry differs significantly in its purpose and content, and serves exclusively the interests of the young family as a one-time material and economic assistance and the basis for their life together from the bride's family.

Thus, the influence of socio-economic transformations on the entire course of history, the history of culture and the psychology of the people, including the marriage and family relations of the Kazakhs, is obvious.

In Kazakhstan's society, which is currently in conditions of intensive economic, socio-political and cultural transformation, along with the trend of increasing freedom to choose an individual lifestyle, there is an "entry" into the daily life of Kazakhs of national values associated with ethnic tradition. Especially clearly, according to the modern Kazakh historian-ethnographer S.H. Shalginbaeva, this is manifested today in the urbanized urban environment of the titular ethnos of the republic. In her dissertation work, she investigated the traditions, customs and rituals of the wedding, maternity and child cycle, currently observed by urban Kazakhs [5, p.13]. These include the following: "*kindik sheshe*" — i.e. the umbilical cord mother or midwife, "*at koyu*" — naming, "*shildehana*" — a holiday on the occasion of the birth of a child, "*besikke salu*" — laying in the cradle, "*kyrkynan shygaru*" — removing a child from *sorokovin*, "*tusau kesu*" — cutting the fetters,

"*sundetke otyrgyzu*" is a ritual circumcision custom associated with the religion – Islam.

According to the results of ethnozoological research, it was revealed that the most stable rituals and customs of the maternity and child cycle in the life of a modern Kazakh family are the rituals — "*kyrkynan shygaru*", "*tusau kesu*", "*sundenke otyrgyzu*".

The modern wedding complex of urban Kazakhs, according to the researcher, is divided into a number of ritual cycles: 1) matchmaking; 2) "seeing off" by the bride's parents ("*kyz uzatu toyu*") at will and material possibilities; 3) solemn registration of marriage and religious ceremony of marriage ("*neke kyyu*") at the request of the young and their parents; 4) the main celebration ("*ulenu toyu*"); 5) "where to *shakyr*", "*kiyt kigyzu*" — a meeting of the bride's parents and relatives (after the main celebration), first at the groom's parents' house, later at the bride's parents and an exchange of gifts; 6) visits of young people to the parents of the bride, as well as to the relatives of the bride and groom, which can be attributed to family-related relations.

At the same time, it is established that in the modern wedding ceremony of urban Kazakhs, the revived rite "*neke kyyu*" is not yet fully an organic part of the Kazakh wedding ceremony.

In the pre-wedding period, Kazakhs observe a number of rituals, rituals and customs - "*oli-tyri*", ("*alive-dead*"), "*korzhyn*" (a saddlebag made of home-spun or carpet fabric), "*syrga salu*", "*alka salu*", "*mandaiga tiyn tagu*" (gifts to the bride), "*ananyn essence*" (payment for mother's milk), "*kiyt*" (literally "to dress"), invariable is the eating of the ritual dish "*kuyryk bauyr*" (liver with a piece of fat), "*toast*" (lamb brisket) and the payment of "*kade*" (gift), it is mandatory to receive a blessing – "*bata alu*" (blessing) from respected and wise people. The performance of the traditional wedding song "*zhar-zhar*", "*shashu*" — the ceremony of showering the newlyweds with various sweets and coins, "*bet ashar*" (opening the bride's face), "*salem beru*" (bow), "*toy bastar*" (a dish with gifts) – all these rituals are associated with the arrangement and conduct of the wedding.

The post-wedding ceremony includes "*otka mai kuyu*" (pouring oil into the fire), "*kelin shai*" — the ceremony of pouring tea to her husband's relatives, "*zhasau*" - the bride's dowry, "*where shakyr*", "*yoshik-tor corset*", "*kelin shakyr*", "*uy corset*".

At the same time, the author has established that according to the rite of "clearing out" in the urban environment, only such an element of this rite as the bride crossing the threshold of the apartment or the house of the groom's parents with her right foot has been preserved. This rite is mainly observed only by the rural population because the urban population, living in residential multi-storey buildings, does not have the opportunity to perform this rite, and is less informed.

The analysis also revealed the characteristic features of the modern institution of marriage among Kazakhs, such as the wide scope of premarital dating and the independent choice of a marriage partner. Nevertheless, the scientist notes, there is a certain significance of the influence of parents on the marriage choice among urban Kazakhs.

Thus, the analysis of the modern wedding ceremony of urban Kazakhs allows us to conclude that elements of traditional culture are preserved in it .

However, it should be noted that several traditions and rituals stand out, to which an ambiguous attitude is manifested.

CONCLUSION OF THE 2ST CHAPTER

In conclusion, mental health problems, cultural and religious differences, and parenting issues are common challenges faced by Kazakh families in maintaining healthy relationships. Mental health problems such as depression, anxiety, and addiction can affect individuals and the family as a whole, leading to communication breakdowns and conflicts. Cultural and religious differences may lead to misunderstandings and conflicting values, making it difficult to find common ground and connect emotionally. Parenting issues such as differing parenting styles and expectations can also cause tension and affect children's mental health and development.

Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach that involves education, awareness, and open communication. Families can seek counseling or therapy to improve their communication and develop coping mechanisms. It is also essential to provide support to those who are struggling with mental health issues, including seeking professional help when needed.

Additionally, education and awareness programs can help families better understand and appreciate cultural and religious differences, promoting mutual respect and understanding. By addressing these challenges proactively, families can create a healthy and supportive environment that fosters strong relationships and promotes mental well-being.

3.3. Research methods and process

In our project, we used research method called survey.

A survey is a structured questionnaire used to gather data from a select group of people. Researchers pre-write surveys with a limited number of questions that may be close-ended or open-ended depending on the information the researcher wants to collect. Some surveys are self-completed, meaning that the survey participant records their answer and submits it to the researcher. Other times, a researcher may administer the survey directly, such as in an interview. Surveys can be an effective method of collecting self-reported data from a large population of participants. Therefore, we provided google forms as the tool for research.

URL Link: <https://forms.gle/MXU-VoBj6Rsj4ikPJ6>

3.4. Result of our research

What do you believe are the most pressing problems facing Kazakh families today?

[Копировать](#)

22 ответа

In your opinion, how does economic hardship (such as poverty and unemployment) impact Kazakh families?

[Копировать](#)

22 ответа

In your opinion, what can be done to strengthen family relationships and improve the overall well-being of Kazakh families?

14 ответов

- Financial help
- idk
- Finance
- pay more money
- Money
- Support from government
- Encouraging open communication, spending quality time together, and promoting mutual respect are some effective ways to achieve this goal
- the first thing I think is to provide people with jobs so that there are no financial difficulties
- taking the risks

Do you think the government is doing enough to address the problems faced by Kazakh families?

Rate from 0 to 5 , 5 - provide full assistance, 0 - there is no help at all

22 ответа

If you have ever encountered problems, what kind of help are you getting now?

22 ответа

CONCLUSION OF THE SURVEY

As you can see from the survey, many respondents have financial difficulties. It is assumed from this that many problems relate to the country's economy, with a lack of support from the government, as well as with poor financial literacy of citizens. In addition, it is worth noting the incorrect distribution of individual values, because many focus on the opinion of society and building a family despite their well-being.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Kazakh families face a range of acute challenges related to the financial system and resources, domestic violence, education, health problems, mental health problems, parenting issues, and cultural and religious differences. These challenges can have significant impacts on individuals and families, leading to stress, conflicts, and even long-term negative effects on mental and physical health.

One of the most significant challenges faced by Kazakh families is the lack of financial resources and the limited opportunities for economic mobility. This can lead to poverty and financial stress, which can negatively impact mental health and relationships. Domestic violence is also a serious problem in Kazakh families, with many women and children experiencing physical and emotional abuse.

Education is another critical issue, with many families struggling to access quality education for their children. Health problems, both physical and mental, can also affect families' well-being and place significant strain on resources. Parenting issues, such as differing parenting styles and expectations, can also lead to tension and affect children's development.

Finally, cultural and religious differences can create challenges in communication and understanding, leading to conflicts and misunderstandings. Addressing these challenges requires a collaborative and multi-faceted approach, including education, awareness, and support for families. By promoting access to resources

and services, increasing awareness and understanding of cultural and religious differences, and providing support for mental health and parenting, families can build stronger relationships and create healthier environments for themselves and their communities.

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